

COST IC1404 WG4
Y1 and Y2 Technical Report WG4.1
CPS Profile - Brainstorming session

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Document History

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V0.1	10/11/2016	VA	Document Created
V0.2	29/12/2016	PC	Added 'Results' section

Introduction

The current report presents the work done in the scope of IC1406's Workgroup 4, with the specific task force dedicated to brainstorming a list of topics that should be covered on a post-graduate course offering on MPM4CPS.

The goal was to come up with the list of topics on MPM4CPS that will (a) be the basis of the post-graduate course program and (b) be the reference of the topics that underlie the knowledge body required of a CPS engineer (focusing on an MPM setting)

The merit of this effort lies in the possibility of coming up with an unbiased taxonomy that would be then be used to validate other undergoing efforts to elicit the list of topics within the WG4.

Methodology

The first step was to brief all the participants about the **goal** of the brainstorm and reach consensus. The participants were also acquainted with the results of the Pilot Assessment that were developed in the scope of WG4 and presented at the previous meeting [\[1\]](#). The process that followed by multiple sessions of nearly free-thinking idea (topic) collection followed by prioritisation and re-arrangement. The session lasted for about 2:30m.

As the session progressed, each participant contributed to a list of topics that were further expanded by other members while exposing their motivations and points of view. The session was carried out with all the members (the co-authors) standing in front of a whiteboard. Each member was given the possibility to update the whiteboard in turn.

Results

The refined taxonomy of subjects is presented below in Table 1 organised according to the topic category. A total of 56 subjects were identified.

The subject category **Fundamental** refers to background engineering (continuous and discrete mathematics, statistics and physics) knowledge that is required of a CPS engineer. These subjects are the basis of most any subject in the coming categories. Then, the category **CPS Core** captures the fundamental knowledge required of a CPS engineer. The rationale is that to be a CPS engineer cannot wear the title without having knowledge of these topics. The category **Core Model-based Systems Engineering** gathers the subjects that are fundamental on Modelling. In particular with multi-paradigm modelling. Then there are three 'Follow-up' categories on **Electronics**, **Computer Science** and **Mechanics** that can be regarded as specialisations of the CPS expert profile.

Some subjects about **Application** areas were identified that due to their pervasiveness should be known to the CPS expert. During the brainstorm, it also became clear that certain Soft-skills are required to be equipped to effectively undertake the responsibility of implementing real-world projects.

Table 1 - List of MPM4CPS subjects organized by category

SUBJECTS BY CATEGORY	TOTAL SUBJECTS
<p>Fundamental</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physics Calculus Differential Equations Linear Algebra Discrete Mathematics Discrete Structures Statistics and Probability Theory Systems Theory and Complexity Logic 	9
<p>Core CPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Models of CPS Control Theory Model-based Testing Electronics Embedded Systems Sensor and Actuator Systems Concurrent and Real-Time Systems Networked Systems Architecture Design and Solution Synthesis Verification and Validation Simulation 	13

Safety Critical Systems	
Optimization Methods	
Core Model-based Systems Engineering	
Modeling Formalisms	4
Modelling Languages and Tools	
Domain Driven Design	
Requirements Engineering	
Follow-up Electronics	
Digital Circuits	2
System on a Chip	
Follow up Mechanics	2
Mechanics	
Thermodynamics	
Follow-up Computer Science	
Algorithms and Data Structures	12
Computer Architecture and Organization	
Software Engineering	
Operating Systems	
Programming Paradigms	
Large Scale Databases	
Human Machine Interaction	
Internet of Things	
Real-Time Data Processing	
Security and Privacy	
Computational Intelligence	
Image Processing and Machine Vision	

Applications	
Factory Plant Automation	8
Smart Grids	
Smart Buildings	
Mechatronics	
Robotics	
Aerospace	
Automotive	
Biomedical and Healthcare Systems	
Soft Skills	
Ethics	8
Writing	
Lifelong Learning	
Project Management	
Decision Theory	
Financial Analysis	
Standards	
Evolution of Cyber Physical Systems	
TOTAL	56

Bibliography

[1] Amaral, Vasco, Carreira, Paulo, Goulão, Miguel, Martinović, Goran, & Banjanovic-Mehmedovic, Lejla. (2016). COST IC1404 WG4 Y1 and Y2 Technical Report WG4.2 CPS profile - Systematic Search. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.223856>